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Heroical Poems in The Track of History Malay Culture: An Analysis of Heroical Values Warriors in The Contemporary Era: A Stylistic Study

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the heroic values in Malay heroic pantun and its relevance to the contemporary era through a stylistic approach. Pantun, as a form of traditional Malay oral literature, contains many cultural and moral values that can be used as references in understanding the concept of heroism in the context of Malay history and culture. This study uses a stylistic analysis method to identify and interpret the language style, structure, and symbols that reflect heroic values in the pantun. The results show that heroic pantun not only describes the courage and sacrifice of the warriors, but also highlights the importance of integrity, wisdom, and collective spirit in facing the challenges of the times. These values remain relevant and can be adapted in the context of the contemporary era, providing inspiration for the younger generation to appreciate and apply the principles of heroism in everyday life.

Keyword: Heroic pantun; Malay culture; Heroic values; Contemporary era; Stylistics

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INTRODUCTION

Pantun is one of the most important forms of traditional poetry in Malay culture. With its distinctive structure, pantun is not only a medium of aesthetic expression but also a means to convey moral, social, and cultural values. In the context of Malay cultural history, heroic rhymes play a significant role as a tool to perpetuate the stories of heroism and the struggles of Malay heroes. These pantuns' heroic values reflect the ethos of struggle, the spirit of patriotism, and the wisdom passed down from generation to generation. Heroic pantun depicts heroic figures who are not only known for their bravery on the battlefield but also for their wisdom, integrity, and devotion to the nation and state. In Malay history, these pantuns have not only become oral history records but also serve as a tool to instill heroic values in the younger generation. Values such as courage, patriotism, justice, and wisdom contained in heroic rhymes are expected to serve as role models for the community (Akbar, 2023; Senen, 2024; Azhari, 2023; Qamari; Andryrestu, 2024; Maisari, 2024; Zikrullah, M., & Azhari, A., 2024; Zulkhairi, 2024).

Heroic rhymes often reflect important events in Malay history's trajectory, such as the struggle against invaders and the effort to maintain independence. For example, the pantun that emerged during the Dutch and British colonization periods depicts many heroic rhymes. A stylistic study of heroic rhymes provides a deeper understanding of how the structure, language style, and symbols used in rhymes can reinforce heroic messages. Through stylistic analysis, we can uncover the creative ways in which poets convey heroic values, as well as how these stylistic elements contribute to the aesthetic and emotive effects of the rhymes (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Paull, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024; Johan, 2024; Ibrahi, 2024).

In the contemporary era, the relevance of heroic rhymes is increasingly important amidst rapid social and cultural changes. Modernization and globalization often bring new challenges to the preservation of traditional values. However, heroic rhymes still have a strong appeal as a cultural heritage rich in noble values. Through this study, it is hoped that heroic rhymes will not only be preserved as part of the literary heritage but also revived as a source of inspiration for the younger generation to face today's challenges. This study aims to examine heroic values in Malay pantun through a stylistic approach, as well as identify the relevance and contribution of heroic pantun in the historical context and contemporary era. Thus, this study is expected to provide new insights into the importance of heroic pantun in strengthening the cultural identity and moral values of the Malay community, as well as highlight the importance of heroic pantun in strengthening the cultural identity and moral values of the Malay community.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Research Perspectives:

Historical and Cultural Perspectives: This research explores the development of the heroic pantun within the historical trajectory of Malay culture. This approach aids in comprehending the historical and cultural milieu in which the pantun originated and operated. The analysis employs a stylistic approach to delve into the language use, style, and structure of pantun as a literary art form.

Major Theories and Concepts:

Heroism Theory: This theory uses concepts of heroism to explain the traits and values of a hero in Malay culture. This theory assists in identifying and analyzing pantun's heroic values. **Stylistic Theory:** This theory provides tools to analyze linguistic and aesthetic aspects of pantun. It includes the analysis of elements such as rhythm, metaphor, simile, alliteration, and narrative structure. **Oral Literature Theory:** Uses this theory to understand pantun as an oral literary form, including the mode of delivery, social function, and the change in oral to written tradition.

Synthesis of Similar Studies:

Studies on Pantun: This study reviews previous research on Malay pantun to understand the general characteristics, themes, and social functions of pantun in Malay society. **Studies on Heroism in Malay Literature:** Synthesize research on the representation of heroism in other Malay literary works such as stories and poetry. **Stylistic Studies:** This book covers research that has been done on stylistic analysis in the context of Malay literature and other relevant literature to identify the most effective methods of analysis.

Summary of Key Issues:

Relevance of Traditional Heroism in Contemporary Contexts: Discusses how the heroic values contained in pantun are relevant or have changed in modern Malay society. **Preservation of Oral**

Culture and Tradition: Identifying Challenges in Preserving Pantun as a Cultural Heritage Amidst Technological Developments and Social Changes Influence of Globalization: Investigating how globalization affects Malay pantun's perception and expression of heroic values.

METHOD

This research uses a descriptive-qualitative approach with a focus on text analysis. We chose this approach to uncover and scrutinize the meaning inherent in the heroic pantun, and to comprehend the stylistic elements that mold its aesthetics and significance. The main data for this research are the texts of heroic pantun collected from various sources, including manuscripts, pantun collection books, and oral recordings. We selected these sources based on their relevance and representation of the theme of heroism in Malay culture. Books, journal articles, and conference papers on pantun, heroism, and stylistics in Malay literature are examples of literature pertinent to the research topic.

We are gathering heroic rhymes from diverse written and digital sources. The literature study also includes collecting literature that discusses the theory of stylistics, heroism in literature, and Malay culture. We analyze the pantun text to pinpoint and explain stylistic elements like language usage, metaphor, simile, alliteration, assonance, and pantun structure. This analysis aims to understand how these elements shape the meaning and aesthetics of heroic rhymes. Using the stylistic analysis, interpret the heroic values contained in the rhymes. The researcher will look for the main themes that appear in the rhymes and relate them to the concept of heroism. Comparing heroic values in Pantun with heroic values in the contemporary era. This analysis involves looking at how these values are relevant and applied in today's context, both in everyday life and in popular culture.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

In this study, we found that heroic pantun in the Malay cultural tradition is not only an entertaining literary work but also carries deep heroic values. We analyze three examples of heroic pantun to understand its symbols, language style, and structure, and to explore heroic values that can be applied in the contemporary era.

1. First rhyme:

...

Jika hujan turun gerimis
Beku hati berubah luka
Pejuang tanpa mengira
Tetap yakin dan setia

...

Symbol, Style, and Structure Analysis

1. Symbol

It's drizzling rain. Drizzling rain often symbolizes sadness or hardship. In this context, it may reflect a difficult or challenging situation faced by the warrior. Frozen heart turned wound: This symbolizes initially stifled or hidden feelings that later turn into real pain. It may depict the suffering and sacrifice experienced by warriors. Selfless warrior: a warrior who fights selflessly or without calculating risks. It highlights the courage and sincerity of the warriors. Remain confident and loyal: This symbolizes strong determination and loyalty, two important values in heroism.

2. Language Style

Metaphor: The use of metaphor is seen in "the rain fell in drizzle" and "frozen hearts turned to wounds," which give an emotional picture of struggle and suffering. Parallelism: In the last two lines, there is a parallel structure that emphasizes the qualities of the warrior. This reinforces the desired values of faith and loyalty. Repetition: The repeated concepts of "warrior" and "confident and loyal" help to emphasize the importance of these values in the context of heroism.

3. Structure

Rhyme and Rhythm: This pantun follows the typical rhyme pattern of Malay pantun (a-b-a-b), which makes it easy to remember and pronounce. This structure also creates a rhythm that

supports the message's delivery. Four Lines: The typical four-line structure of a pantun provides a dense yet meaningful message, utilizing word economy to convey heroic values.

Heroic Values in the Contemporary Era

This pantun highlights some heroic values that remain relevant in the contemporary era: Courage: a warrior who does not calculate risks and continues to fight even in adversity. Sincerity and selflessness: a warrior who acts without expecting anything in return. Firmness and Loyalty: Unwavering faith and loyalty – these values are important in facing the challenges of modern times.

Influence on the Younger Generation

Inspiration and Role Model: These rhymes can be a source of inspiration for the younger generation, providing examples of the importance of courage, sincerity, and loyalty. Cultural Preservation: Reading and understanding this pantun also helps the younger generation appreciate and preserve Malay cultural heritage. Moral Values: This pantun teaches strong moral values, which can be applied in daily life by the younger generation.

2. *Second Pantun:*

...

Padi dipipis belum kuning
Pejuang belum sampai ke punting
Dalam berjuang jangan berputus asa
Harum nama sentiasa dihargai

...

Symbol, Style, and Structure Analysis

1. *Symbol*

Paddy is not yet yellow. Immature rice is symbolic of an unfinished process or an endeavor that has not yet reached its peak. It depicts a phase of struggle that has not yet reached the final goal. The fighter has not yet reached the punting point. Punting refers to the tip of the ripe paddy, symbolizing success or final achievement. A warrior who has not yet reached punting means a warrior who has not yet achieved full success. A fragrant name describes a good name that remains remembered and cherished. It is a symbol of lasting honor and recognition for a warrior.

2. *Language Style*

Parallelism: The first and second lines, as well as the third and fourth lines, have parallel structures. This gives an orderly and harmonious rhythm. Metaphor: the use of paddy and punting as metaphors for the journey and achievements of a warrior. Imperative: "In striving, do not despair" is a form of imperative that provides advice and motivation. Allegory: From the start of the effort to achieving honor, the entire pantun serves as an allegory of a warrior's life journey.

3. *Structure of*

First and Second Lines: A cover that contains metaphorical allusions or images of nature. Third and Fourth Lines: The body part that conveys the message or main value of the rhyme, in this case, about perseverance in fighting and respect for good name.

Heroic Values in the Contemporary Era

Resilience and Persistence: This value is very relevant in the context of modern struggles, whether in education, career, or social activism. Young people in the contemporary era encounter numerous challenges, and this rhyme encourages them to persevere. Respect and Honor: It teaches that sincere and persistent struggle will always be rewarded. This is relevant in the context of building society's reputation and integrity. Patience in the Process: It reminds us that success takes time and process, an important value in an era where the younger generation is often looking for instant results.

Influence on the Young Generation

Motivation and Inspiration: These rhymes can serve as a source of motivation for the younger generation, teaching the importance of perseverance and grit. Cultivation of Traditional Values: It helps preserve cultural heritage and traditional values, bridging the past with the present. Character Building: Through the values taught, this pantun plays a role in shaping character

and a strong work ethic in the younger generation. This analysis illustrates how heroic rhymes contain important values that are still relevant for today's youth, as well as providing an understanding of the stylistic elements that enrich the meaning of the rhymes.

3. *The Third Pantun:*

Terjantai lidah bertukar lidah
Sejarah Melayu menurut pukah
Pejuang teguh tangan tak lemah
Iman dan takwa bawa berjaya

Symbol, Style, and Structure Analysis

1. *Symbol*

This expression, "Dangling tongues exchange tongues," describes the communication and diplomacy skills possessed by the warrior. "Tongue," as a symbol of language and communication, shows the importance of speaking and dialogue skills in the struggle. Malay history, according to Pukah, refers to the heritage and stories of the past that form the basis of the nation's identity and pride. "Pukah" (change or journey) symbolizes a historical journey full of dynamics and challenges. Pejuang teguh tangan tak lemah: "Strong fighters" symbolizes the strength, courage, and determination of the heroes. "Hands are not weak," meaning they do not give up easily and have a high fighting spirit. Faith and piety bring victory. "Faith and piety" symbolizes the spiritual and moral values that are the foundation for achieving glory or success.

2. *Language Style:*

Alliteration: As seen in "Dangling tongues exchange tongues," the repetition of the consonants "t" and "l" creates a distinctive rhythm and emphasizes the importance of communication. Parallelism: The repetitive structure of "The warrior's firm hand is not weak" emphasizes the warrior's strength and determination. Metaphors are used to describe physical and mental toughness, such as "hands are not weak." The phrase "faith and piety bring victory" highlights the spiritual aspect as a key to success, which may not always be perceived as a struggle in a physical context.

3. *Structure:*

Quatrain: This pantun follows the traditional structure of a Malay pantun with four lines. The final rhyme follows the pattern of a-a-a-a, which gives harmony and unity to the pantun. Each line conveys a clear moral message about the importance of communication, respect for history, consistency in struggle, and spiritual values.

Heroic Values in the Contemporary Era

Courage and Resilience: This rhyme emphasizes that courage and resilience are still relevant and important in facing today's challenges. Communication Skills: In the globalization and digital era, communication skills are key in resolving conflicts and building collaboration. Respect for History: Appreciating history and learning from the past helps the younger generation to not repeat the same mistakes and take lessons from the heroes. Spiritual Values: Faith and piety as moral foundations are still considered important to maintain integrity and motivation in contemporary struggles.

Influence on the Younger Generation

Motivation and Inspiration: This pantun can be a source of inspiration for the younger generation to adopt heroic values in their daily lives. Cultural Understanding: Reintroducing heroic rhymes helps the younger generation understand and appreciate their cultural heritage. Character Building: The values reflected in the rhymes can help shape a character that is strong, courageous, and has integrity.

Discussion

From time to time, heroic pantun has become an integral part of Malay literary heritage, reflecting the values, morality, and aspirations of the Malay people. This study aims to identify and analyze the heroic values contained in Malay pantun and relate their relevance to the contemporary era through a stylistic approach. Heroic values contained in pantun, such as

resilience, hard work, faith, and piety, remain relevant in the contemporary era. Amidst the challenges of globalization, rapid social change, and economic pressures, these values provide moral guidance that can help the younger generation better direct their lives. Resilience and hard work as heroic values provide an example for young people not to give up easily and to continue to strive toward achieving their goals despite facing various obstacles. This is especially important in the context of increasingly fierce and dynamic global competition.

Faith and piety underscore the importance of spirituality in modern life. While technology and material progress have changed many aspects of life, spiritual values remain a solid moral foundation for individuals and society as a whole. This pantun's message reminds the younger generation of the importance of maintaining a balance between material achievements and spiritual happiness. Heroic pantun can serve as a moral and cultural education tool for the younger generation. By integrating pantun into the education curriculum, the younger generation can learn to appreciate their cultural heritage as well as internalize the heroic values taught. This can help shape a character that is strong, has integrity, and is committed to noble values.

Interpretation of Findings

This research reveals that heroic pantun in Malay culture does not only function as a means of entertainment but also as an important medium for transmitting heroic values from generation to generation. The heroic pantun studied demonstrates a rich use of language, with symbolism and metaphors that reinforce moral and ethical messages about courage, honesty, and sacrifice. This is in line with previous findings by Rahim (2010), who stated that Malay oral literature has a central role in the character education of its people.

Through stylistic analysis, we found that these rhymes often use repetitive structures and parallelism that strengthen their memorability and appeal. This style of language makes it easier to recall and convey heroic values to a wider audience. For example, the use of alliteration and assonance is found in pantuns that tell the stories of heroes, such as Hang Tuah, which emphasize courage and loyalty as key values.

Comparison with Previous Literature

This study's results align with previous research demonstrating the frequent use of pantun and other traditional poetic forms to communicate social and moral values (Sweeney, 1998). However, this study adds a new dimension by highlighting the relevance of these values in a contemporary context. For example, in more modern countries, values such as courage and sacrifice are linked to the fight against social injustice and corruption, reflecting the challenges facing society today. Furthermore, this study demonstrates a progression in the portrayal of heroic values. In modern pantun, there is a tendency to link heroic stories with national identity and political struggle, reflecting the shifting social and political context in contemporary Malay society.

Research Implications

These findings have significant implications of these findings are quite significant in the context of cultural preservation and education. Pantun, as part of the Malay cultural heritage, has great potential to be used as a character education tool in schools. By integrating heroic pantun in the curriculum, values such as courage, honesty, and sacrifice can be instilled in the younger generation in an interesting and memorable way. Furthermore, this discovery has implications for cultural preservation efforts. Given that pantun is a form of oral literature that is vulnerable to extinction, the excavation and documentation of heroic pantun are very important. This can be done through collaboration between academics, the government, and cultural communities to ensure that this literary heritage remains alive and relevant to today's society.

Limitations of the Study

While this research offers a profound understanding of heroic values in Malay pantun, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Firstly, this study is limited to a stylistic analysis and does not cover the performative aspects of pantun, which are also important in a full understanding of its function in society. Further ethnographic studies that include direct observation of pantun performances may provide a more holistic understanding. Secondly, the pantun samples analyzed in this study may not fully represent the diversity of existing heroic pantuns. Further research with a wider and more diverse sample from various regions of the Malay world may enrich these findings and analyses.

Further Research Opportunities

Future research can expand on this study by exploring the relationship between heroic pantun and other forms of oral literature, such as poetry and gurindam. In addition, further research can focus on the performative analysis of pantun, including how pantun is presented in various social and cultural contexts, as well as how audiences respond to and interpret the values conveyed. Research can also deepen our understanding of the impact of globalization on heroic pantun. For instance, the impact of digital media and popular culture shapes the delivery and reception of heroic rhymes among the younger generation. Thus, this research not only contributes to the academic understanding of heroic pantun but also to practical efforts for the preservation and revitalization of Malay cultural heritage.

Research Significance

Impact on the general public. Cultural Preservation: This research can aid efforts to preserve Malay cultural heritage, particularly heroic rhymes, by documenting and analyzing them. **Education:** We can use the research results as educational materials to impart the values of heroism and Malay culture to the younger generation, enhancing their familiarity and appreciation of their cultural heritage. **Identity Pride:** By understanding the heroic values in their own culture, the Malay community can increase their sense of pride in their cultural identity. **Impact on Scientific and Academic Development: Theoretical Contribution:** This research can add theoretical insights into the field of Malay literature and cultural studies, particularly in the stylistic approach and analysis of heroic values. **Literature enrichment:** This study will increase the amount of literature available on pantun and heroism in Malay culture, which can be used as a reference for future studies. **Methodology:** Other studies that employ similar methods in different cultural contexts can refer to the approach and methods employed in this study. **Practical Benefits: Curriculum Development:** This study's findings can enhance the richness of local cultural and historical values in educational curricula. This research can help promote Malay cultural tourism by increasing understanding and appreciation of pantun and heroic values.

CONCLUSION

This research explores the heroic values contained in Malay pantun and their relevance to the present cultural and social context. By using a descriptive qualitative approach and stylistic analysis, this study succeeded in identifying the dominant stylistic elements in heroic pantun and interpreting the heroic values hidden in it. This research concludes with the following findings: **Heroism in Malay Pantun:** Malay Pantun is not only a linguistically beautiful literary work but also a medium rich in heroic values. Text analysis revealed that pantun frequently portrays tales of valiant and honorable heroes and warriors. **Stylistic Elements:** This study's stylistic analysis revealed the use of various language styles and literary techniques in heroic rhymes, including distinctive diction, beautiful rhyme patterns, and powerful metaphors. These elements give the pantun's literary art form depth and richness of meaning to the pantun as a literary art form. **Relevance to the Contemporary Era:** Although Malay pantun has deep roots in Malay history and culture, the heroic values contained in it are still relevant to the present. This research demonstrates the continued significance and applicability of values like courage, loyalty, and sacrifice in various cultural and societal contexts. **Implications and Recommendations:** The results of this study have important implications in the fields of education, cultural preservation, and the development of Malay literature. We recommend integrating heroic pantun into the educational curriculum, supporting initiatives for the preservation and promotion of Malay culture, and encouraging further research in the analysis of heroic values in Malay literature.

Thus, this study not only contributes to the understanding of heroic pantun in the trajectory of Malay cultural history but also provides valuable insights for the development of Malay literary and cultural studies more broadly. Understanding the heroic values in Malay pantun aims to enhance the community's appreciation and enrichment of their cultural heritage, while also perpetuating the tradition of honoring heroes and warriors in this captivating literary art form.

Recommendation for Future Research

Continuing the Study of Stylistic Analysis: Develop further research in the stylistic analysis of Malay pantun to deepen the understanding of the use of language and style in this traditional literary work. This could include further investigation of specific elements, such as the use of metaphor, comparison, or rhythm in pantun. Development of a Comparative Study Model: Explore a model of study that compares Malay heroic pantun with heroic literary works from other cultures or different historical periods. This will assist in understanding the universal and unique aspects of the heroic values contained in Malay pantun.

Deeper Cultural and Historical Studies: Conduct more in-depth research on the cultural and historical context that shaped the Malay heroic pantun, including the influence of various historical events, oral traditions, and inherited cultural values. Application of Heroic Values in Education: This study explores the potential use of Malay heroic pantun as a learning resource to introduce and foster understanding of heroic values in both formal and informal education. Interdisciplinary Studies: Encourage interdisciplinary approaches in research on Malay heroic pantun, such as combining literary analysis with historical studies, cultural anthropology, or cultural psychology, to gain a more holistic understanding of this phenomenon. With these recommendations in mind, future researchers are expected to deepen and expand their knowledge of Malay heroic pantun and make meaningful contributions to the understanding and preservation of this cultural heritage.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ahmad, R., & Ismail, Z. (2021). The Role of Malay Pantun in Promoting Heroic Values in Contemporary Society. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 52(3), 123-145.
- Akbar, M. (2023). Scholarship Information Service on UIN Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh Website. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(1), 124-129.
- Alwi, M. S., & Ramli, H. (2022). Pantun Kepahlawanan dan Pembentukan Karakter Generasi Muda: Studi Kasus di Sekolah Menengah Atas. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Melayu*, 12(3), 145-160.
- Andyrestu, A. (2024). Translation Equivalence in the Song "Mine" by Petra Sihombing with the Indonesian Version. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 6(1), 001-012.
- Anwar, Z., & Latif, R. (2024). Interpreting Heroic Values in Modern Context: A Stylistic Analysis of Malay Pantun. *Journal of Modern Literature and Cultural Studies*, 9(2), 123-140.
- Arifin, Syahrul. (2021). Stilistika dalam Puisi Melayu: Analisis Estetika dan Nilai Moral. *Jurnal Sastra dan Budaya*, Vol. 15, No. 2.
- Arshad, M. R., & Karim, N. A. (2021). Exploring the Heroic Values in Malay Literature: A Study on Pantun and Folklore. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 52(3), 411-429.
- Azhari, A., Athaillah, Q. B., & Manizal, Y. (2023). Investigasi Kejahatan dalam Novel "Azh-Zhill Al Aswad" Karya Najib Kailani (Studi Linguistik Forensik). *An-Nahdah Al-'Arabiyah*, 3(2), 147-176.
- Azmi, R. M., & Mahmud, W. A. W. (2021). The Influence of Traditional Malay Poetry on Youth Values in Contemporary Malaysia. *Journal of Malay Studies*, 12(2), 45-62.
- Chua, Y. P., & Abdullah, S. (2022). Stylistic Analysis of Traditional Malay Poetry: Reflections on Modern Heroism. *International Journal of Literary Studies*, 10(1), 67-89.
- Cristina, G. (2024). The Acehese Folklore and Social Behavior. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 51-60.
- Fadly, A. S. (2024). Analisis Fungsi Bahasa Geoffrey Leech dalam Indang Nagari Muaro Paneh. *Tilistika: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra*, 17(1), 57-68.
- Fitria, Ayu. (2023). Nilai Kepahlawanan dan Relevansinya di Era Modern: Perspektif Sastra Melayu. *Jurnal Literasi dan Pendidikan*, Vol. 8, No. 3.

- Hanafiah, R. (2022). Stilistika dalam Pantun Kepahlawanan: Kajian Terhadap Struktur dan Makna. *Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra Melayu*, 15(2), 98-115
- Hartati, L., Liana, L., & Rozani, M. (2024). Kearifan Lokal Masyarakat Bangka Belitung dalam Cerita Rakyat "Batu Balai": Kajian Pendidikan Karakter. *Stilistika: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra*, 17(1), 1-10. doi:10.30651/st.v17i1.20971.
- Hasan, M. N., & Rahman, A. A. (2020). Symbolism and Heroic Values in Malay Oral Literature: An Analysis of Pantun. *Southeast Asian Journal of Cultural Studies*, 8(1), 78-95.
- Ibrahi, A. (2024). The Teumatok Culture in Aceh Singkil. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 1-8.
- Ibrahim, H., & Yusuf, M. (2023). Contemporary Reflections on Traditional Malay Heroism: A Stylistic Study of Pantun. *Journal of Malay Cultural Studies*, 11(4), 275-292.
- Ibrahim, Z. A. (2021). Stilistika dalam Pantun Melayu: Analisis Terhadap Nilai Kepahlawanan. *Journal of Malay Literature*, 29(2), 98-113.
- Ismail, M. (2020). Peranan Pantun dalam Membangun Karakter Bangsa. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*, 25(3), 189-207.
- Jamil, A. (2023). Digitalisasi Pantun Melayu: Peluang dan Tantangan. *Jurnal Teknologi dan Kebudayaan*, 17(1), 123-139.
- Johan, D. (2024). The Keuneunong Dating and Acehnese Society. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 21-30.
- Kamal, N. A., & Yusuf, A. H. (2022). Stilistika dalam Puisi Tradisional: Kajian terhadap Pantun Kepahlawanan Melayu. *Journal of Literature and Culture*, 15(3), 123-138.
- Mahmud, S., & Hassan, N. (2022). Stylistic Analysis of Malay Pantun: Unveiling Cultural and Heroic Elements. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 1234514(1), 56-70.
- Maisari, Y. (2024). The Role of Teachers in Increasing Interest in Learning Arabic in Madrasah Aliyah 6 Aceh Besar. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(2), 161-170.
- Munidar, F. (2024). The Acehnese Literature and Social Behavior. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 31-40.
- Nasir, M. H., & Siti, N. A. (2023). Relevansi Pantun Kepahlawanan di Era Globalisasi: Sebuah Tinjauan Kontemporer. *Jurnal Kebudayaan Melayu Modern*, 14(1), 67-84.
- Nurhayati, S. (2020). Nilai Kepahlawanan dalam Pantun: Perspektif Sejarah dan Budaya. *Jurnal Sejarah dan Budaya*, 10(2), 57-74.
- Paull, J. (2024). The Impact of Coffee Shops on Aceh's Economic Sustainability. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 41-50.
- Putri, Anggraini. (2024). Peran Sastra Tradisional dalam Membentuk Karakter Generasi Muda. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*, Vol. 9, No. 1.
- Qamari, A. S., & Harahap, N. (2024). The Influence of Social Media on the Culture of Saying Islamic Greetings in Mtsn 1 Banda Aceh Students. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(2), 140-147.
- Rafiq, Z. H., & Ahmad, S. N. (2023). Contemporary Relevance of Traditional Malay Poetry among the Youth: A Study of Pantun and Syair. *International Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 123459(4), 89-105.
- Rahim, H., & Noor, M. (2023). Cultural Heritage and Modern Values: A Study of Malay Heroic Pantun. *Journal of Cultural Studies*, 28(2), 198-220.

- Rahim, N., & Abdullah, A. (2020). The Role of Pantun in Preserving Malay Cultural Heritage and Heroism. *Asian Culture and History*, 12(2), 88-95.
- Rahim, N., & Abdullah, A. (2020). The Role of Pantun in Preserving Malay Cultural Heritage and 12345Heroism. *Asian Culture and History*, 12(2), 88-95.
- Rahmadani, A. (2024). The Writing Culture of Scholars of The Aceh kingdom. *Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)*, 1(1), 9-20.
- Rahman, T. (2024). Pantun sebagai Media Pendidikan Karakter di Era Digital. *Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter*, 19(4), 234-250.
- Ramli, A. (2020). Analisis Stilistika dalam Puisi Tradisional Melayu: Makna dan Fungsi. *Jurnal Penelitian Bahasa dan Sastra*, Vol. 12, No. 4.
- Rashid, S. K. (2020). Kepahlawanan dalam Sastra Melayu: Dari Pantun hingga Cerita Rakyat. *Southeast Asian Literature Review*, 8(4), 220-235.
- Salim, F. M., & Ibrahim, H. (2024). Pantun as a Reflection of Heroism and Moral Values in Modern Malay Society. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 11(1), 54-70.
- Sari, W. (2021). Pemanfaatan Media Sosial untuk Melestarikan Pantun Kepahlawanan. *Jurnal Komunikasi dan Budaya*, 14(3), 145-160.
- Senen, I. (2024). The Effect of Method Pedagogy and English Teaching Learning. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(2), 171-190.
- Suryani, Melati. (2022). Kepahlawanan dalam Sastra Melayu: Studi Kasus Pantun dan 12345Hikayat. *Jurnal Kebudayaan Nusantara*, Vol. 10, No. 1.
- Yusof, N. A., & Hashim, R. (2020). Revisiting Malay Heroic Literature: Contemporary Relevance and Stylistic Features. *Malay Literature Journal*, 35(1), 80-102.
- Yusoff, N. S., & Ahmad, F. A. (2024). Pantun sebagai Media Pendidikan Karakter: Studi pada Komunitas Melayu di Malaysia. *Journal of Cultural Studies*, 11(1), 39-56.
- Zainuddin, H. (2023). Tradisi Lisan dalam Konteks Globalisasi: Studi Kasus Pantun Kepahlawanan. *Jurnal Budaya dan Globalisasi*, 18(2), 215-230.
- Zikrullah, M., & Azhari, A. (2024). The critical thinking research trend in Indonesia's language education journals. *Diksi*, 32(1), 107-128.
- Zulhairi, Z., Zulhelmi, A., Azhari, A., Sumardi, S., & Shaliha, C. A. A. (2024). The Acehese Language Use in South Aceh Regency: A Sociolinguistic Analysis. *Buletin Al-Turas*, 30(1).
- Zulkifli, A. (2021). Estetika dan Makna dalam Pantun Kepahlawanan. *Jurnal Estetika Nusantara*, 9(1), 33-50.